

Librarians as Architects of Intellectual Freedom and Ethical Use of Information: The Case of Private University in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This article examines the role of librarians as architects of intellectual freedom and the ethical use of information in private universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study investigates the contributions of librarians in promoting intellectual freedom, ensuring ethical information use, and the challenges impeding these efforts.

Method: The study adopted a descriptive survey research method, with a research population of 39 librarians. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, and the collected data were analysed using descriptive statistical tools, including tables, frequencies, and means.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that librarians in private universities in Oyo State actively promote intellectual freedom among their users and strive to ensure ethical information use. However, several challenges hinder these efforts. The key barriers to intellectual freedom include poor library funding, censorship, and internet filtering. Similarly, the challenges affecting the ethical use of information include a lack of understanding of ethical codes, concerns about data privacy, restrictions arising from intellectual property rights, and technological complexities.

Implications: The study highlights the critical role of librarians in upholding intellectual freedom and ethical information use. However, overcoming the identified challenges is

essential to ensuring a free flow of information and adherence to ethical standards in library practices.

Conclusion: The study underscores the need for continuous efforts to strengthen intellectual freedom and ethical information use in private university libraries. Addressing the challenges will enhance access to information and improve compliance with ethical guidelines.

Recommendations: The study recommends that targeted interventions be implemented to address the identified challenges, including improved library funding, policy adjustments to reduce censorship and internet filtering, increased awareness of ethical codes, and enhanced support for data privacy and intellectual property rights compliance. Ensuring these measures will foster a more inclusive and ethically responsible information environment.

Key Words: Censorship, Ethical use, Information, Intellectual freedom, Internet filtering, Librarians

Introduction

Intellectual freedom allows for the unhindered access to information, and this helps to create new knowledge and bring about innovation. For Crabtree (2024), intellectual freedom refers to the state of being free to exercise the rights to seek whatever information one needs; while Jackson, Heath and Heath (2024) see it as the ability to receive the information, and the capacity to express ideas the way people choose, without fear or favour. Intellectual freedom, like all other rights, ensures that in exercising these rights, people do not infringe on the rights of others. Sadly, despite the necessities of being intellectually free, there are several inhibiting factors to intellectual freedom. These for Jackson, et. al (2024), Munyao (2024), and Suzuki, Diuguid and Ward (2023) include censorship, disinformation, monitoring, and intolerance, just to mention a few. However, it should be noted that intellectual freedom is essential because it ensures personal growth and development, critical thinking and problem solving skills; leading to creativity and innovation.

In exercising their intellectual freedom, people must learn to do so within the laws, and observe necessary ethical guidelines. The ethical use of information allows that information must be used in a responsible way, making sure that information is accurate,

reliable; Indah and Rizka (2024) averred that the source of the information must be acknowledged by means of proper citation and referencing. Citation and referencing are not enough reasons to plagiarize any piece of information; it must be used within acceptable limits, and ensure fair use. This is because unethical use of information leads to misinformation, breach of privacy, loss of trust, and plagiarism (Cardoso, Miguel and Modolo, 2022).

Ethical use of information refers to the responsible, legal, and fair handling of information in research, education, and everyday communication. Raudhoh and Tri (2024) noted that based on the librarians' code of ethics, ethical use of information includes respecting intellectual property rights, ensuring accuracy, acknowledging sources, and avoiding misinformation or misuse. To ensure that library users strive for intellectual freedom so as to create more knowledge, and do this ethically, librarians must be at the fore of the campaign, because they are the architects of the purviews of intellectual freedom and ethical use of information.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this are to:

1. determine the roles of librarians in the attainment of intellectual freedom; and
2. determine the roles of librarians in ensuring ethical use of information

Review of Related Literature

Dihaa, et. al (2024) noted that intellectual property rights and academic freedom are critical for the promotion of global innovation and intellectual conversations. The researchers examined the interplay between intellectual property rights and academic freedom, because of the complicated legal and ethical issues in the use of copyrighted materials; and a complicated ecosystem in which intellectual property regulations clash with academic freedom values. For Taiwo and Sulyman (2022) the importance of intellectual freedom in collection development practices help to address the issues of censorship and internet filtering. Oberg (2023) averred that intellectual freedom includes a wide range of rights that are interconnected, and these rights include freedom to read, freedom to speak, freedom of expression, freedom of the press, freedom to know, and social responsibility.

Similarly, Oltmann (2018) noted that Code of Ethics for Librarians by the American Library Association has eight principles that focused on equitable service, intellectual freedom, privacy and confidentiality, intellectual property, respect for co-workers, private interests, personal beliefs, and excellence in the profession. Alongside the Code of Ethics is another document, the Core Values of Librarianship. These core values are access, confidentiality/privacy, democracy, diversity, education and lifelong learning, intellectual freedom, preservation, the public good, professionalism, service, and social responsibility. For Raudhoh and Tri (2024), the librarians' codes of ethics are rules that must be obeyed by librarians in order to maintain their dignity, image and professional standing when it comes to rendering services to their users.

Intellectual freedom has as a consequence, the ethical use of information. Campos (2022) sees ethical use of information as the responsible and moral utilization of information, while also ensuring that it is accurate, transparent, respectful, fair, and accountable. The ethical use of information is useful in several contexts, including health, academic, journalism, business, and personal income (Okka, 2024). Judijanto, Utama and Setiyawan (2025) noted that the unethical use of information can lead to the creation and dissemination of deep fakes - manipulated media that can deceive viewers into believing false information.

Little wonder Sushil (2024) noted that ethical considerations include confidentiality, intellectual freedom, and professional conducts, stressing on the importance of effective communication, interpersonal skills, and adaptability in navigating the evolving landscape of library services. On the challenges to intellectual freedom, Opesanwo and Awofeso (2023) revealed that prison inmates in Nigeria have several information needs, despite these numerous needs, prison libraries provide only a limited access to information, constantly censoring the information access, and even outrightly refusing some inmates access to information. Awuor, Okoth and Kwanya (2024) noted that the availability of technologies and their recent advancements have enriched the information landscape, ushering in ethical concerns involving responsible use of technology.

Methodology

The research adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is the 39 librarians in the Private Universities in Oyo State; and the research adopted a total enumeration technique. The data gathering instrument adopted for the study was the questionnaire, hosted on Google Form. The instrument was validated for face and content validation by an expert librarian, before it was sent to the respondents. The data were analysed using statistical tools of tables and means, presented in Tables. The four (4) point Likert scale of measurement was adopted to ascertain the roles of librarians in ensuring intellectual freedom and information ethics in private universities in Oyo State. The Criterion Mean is 2.5; hence the decision rule is that items with Mean values of 2.5 and above were accepted, while those with Mean values lesser than 2.5 were rejected.

Table 1: Research Population

Private Universities in Oyo State	Number of Librarians
Ajayi Crowther	10
Atiba	3
Dominican	5
Dominion	3
Kola Daisi	3
Lead City	10
Precious Cornerstone	5
Total	39

Results Presentation

A total of 35 responses were received from the online questionnaire. This gave a response rate of 90%. The analyses of the research are based on the responses from the 35 librarians that responded to the questionnaire.

Table 2: Roles of librarians in the attainment of intellectual freedom

Strong Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA), Strongly Disagree (SD)					
Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
Intellectual Freedom					
I allow library users the opportunity to freely explore information resources	31	2	1	1	3.77
I advocate for a balance between copyright privileges and intellectual freedom	12	11	10	2	2.94
I encourage access to information resources of all sorts in the library so as to drive innovation	33	2	0	0	3.94
I allow intellectual freedom because it furthers the purpose of education through enquiry	32	3	0	0	3.91
I encourage intellectual freedom because it prevents indoctrination by allowing independent thinking	31	3	1	0	3.83
I advocate for intellectual freedom because it allows library users access to information that contribute to their personal growth and fulfillment	29	5	0	1	3.77
Intellectual freedom enhances the participatory roles of students in class	11	3	15	6	2.54
Grand Mean					3.53

Table 2 revealed the roles librarians play in ensuring intellectual freedom by library clienteles in Private Universities in Oyo State.

For intellectual freedom, the librarians encouraged the access to information resources of all sorts in the library so as to drive innovation (Mean = 3.94), they allowed intellectual freedom because it furthers the purpose of education through enquiry (Mean = 3.91), and they also encouraged intellectual freedom because it prevents indoctrination by allowing

independent thinking (Mean = 3.81); they allowed library users the opportunity to freely explore information resources (Mean = 3.77), and they also advocated for intellectual freedom because it allows library users access to information that contribute to their personal growth and fulfillment (Mean = 3.77); the librarians in private universities in Oyo State advocated for a balance between copyright privileges and intellectual freedom (Mean = .91), as well as strove to ensure intellectual freedom because it enhances the participatory roles of students in class (Mean = 2.54).

Thus, on a general note, the librarians in private universities in Oyo State made significant efforts to advance the concept of intellectual freedom among their users. This is evident as 3.53 is Grand Mean for the category. Hence, based on the decision rule to accept Mean values that are equal to or greater than the criterion Mean of 2.5, we accept that the librarians in private universities in Oyo State are significantly striving to ensure intellectual freedom in their users.

Table 3: Roles of librarians in the attainment of ethical use of information

Strong Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA), Strongly Disagree (SD)

<i>Information Ethics</i>	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
I provide service to all library users through appropriate and usefully organised resources	33	2	0	0	3.94
I provide equitable service to all library users	35	0	0	0	4.0
I provide assistance to all library users in accordance with appropriate policies	28	2	3	2	3.6
I provide the highest level of service to all library users through equitable access	35	0	0	0	4.0
I render unbiased information service to all library users	35	0	0	0	4.0
I protect each library user's right to privacy and confidentiality with respect to information sought or received	35	0	0	0	4.0
I protect each library user's right to privacy and confidentiality with respect to information consulted or borrowed	35	0	0	0	4.0
Grand Mean					3.93

Table 3 revealed the roles librarians play in ensuring the ethical use of information by library clientele in Private Universities in Oyo State.

For ethical use of information, the librarians in private universities in Oyo State provided equitable service to all library users (Mean = 4.00), they also provided the highest level of service to all library users through equitable access (Mean = 4.00), and they render unbiased information service to all library users (Mean = 4.00); similarly, they protected each library user's right to privacy and confidentiality with respect to information sought or received (Mean = 4.00), they protected each library user's right to privacy and confidentiality with respect to information consulted or borrowed (Mean = 4.00), and they provided services to all library users through appropriate and usefully organised resources (Mean = 3.94); they assisted all library users in accordance with appropriate policies (Mean = 3.60).

With a Grand Mean of 3.93 for the category, the research infers that librarians in private universities in Oyo State are striving to ensure the ethical use of information by their library users. Thus, following the decision rule to accept Mean values that are equal to or greater than the criterion Mean of 2.5, we accept that the librarians in private universities in Oyo State are advancing the cause for the ethical use of information.

Discussions of Results

The findings on intellectual freedom agree with Dihaa, et. al (2024). They reported that international legal frameworks should strive to strike a careful balance that will guarantee intellectual property rights, as well as ensure academic freedom values, as strict intellectual property rights hampers academic research and cooperation, while too lax intellectual property rights discourages incentives for innovations. However, the findings of this research contract those of Muhammed, Akinosho and Arilesere (2022). They reported that university libraries in Kwara State have not fully adopted intellectual freedom, and the library bill of rights, the code of ethics, the freedom of information, access to information, and copyright laws are not effective among undergraduates through the use of academic libraries.

The findings on ethical use of information are in agreement with of Taiwo, et, al (2022) who investigated the awareness and use of intellectual freedom policy in academic libraries in Ilorin Metropolis, and reported that concerns on intellectual freedom affect major library processes like the collection development, freedom of expression, access to information, confidentiality, and privacy. Nonetheless, the findings of this research contradict those of Opesanwo and Awofeso (2023). They investigated prison libraries, intellectual freedom and social justice in Nigeria; they reported that despite the huge

information needs of prison inmates in Nigeria, prison libraries provide very few of them, restricting access to information to a majority of the inmates.

Conclusion

Thus, as architects of intellectual freedom and ethical use of information, librarians ensure that there is access to information, for all who need and seek information, and this equitable access to information help in the creation of new knowledge; librarians also ensure that the information so sort and accessed by library users is used ethically.

Intellectual freedom are the rights that allow people to freely seek information, receive the information so sought after, and express their ideas without any form of restrictions or fear of being punished. In like vein, ethical use of information refers to the use of information in a responsible way.

Hence, it should be noted that that library users who seek to have intellectual freedom and use information freely, should also note that they must be responsible in the way the use information. They must acknowledge the sources they got any information from. To this end, librarians must play the part of architects, ensuring all the facets in intellectual freedom as well as in ethical use of information are brought to bear before library users so they can know the implications to their choices, actions, and inactions.

Recommendations

The research recommends that:

1. Library stakeholders should discourage censorship and internet filtering in academic libraries to foster academic cooperation, access to diverse information, and innovation.
2. Librarians should understand and promote ethical codes, ensuring library users adhere to these standards while balancing intellectual property rights for academic access.

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